

CITY SPACES – A NEW LINE OF QUESTIONING

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ABSTRACT

There is no singular solution, or definition, for space within a city centre; when discussing design proposals for a site, it should be as pertinent to seek a new methodology of understanding perceptions & users of a space, as it is to create a design solution. Users, daily activity and patterns of movement become a performance of what space can be, in turn, they can provide the tools to re-address the design landscapes of our cities. They can ask the questions.

A commissioned design project, entitled ‘Trellis’, puts forward a new framework for the definition of urban spaces in Glasgow city centre. Working primarily with the boundaries of long-term, empty sites to create temporary perimeter proposals the project aims to create a design discussion about the potential of permanent public realm development. This design project demonstrates how a form of critical questioning has progressed into an overall conceptual approach, which communicates more than just answers.

Whilst the Trellis project produced a three-dimensional design proposal, this paper focuses on the research methodology behind that proposal. There is scope for this process and project to inform new thinking within public realm design; that enables multiple audiences to interpret and read city space across perception and performance, to create more inclusive urban design.

In doing so, providing the potential to find answers within the questions posed by space in any city centre.

PERCEPTION, SPACE, POTENTIAL

1.1 WHAT IS THE POTENTIAL FOR SPACE?

In the simplest terms, it can be concluded that space in our cities is something perceived differently by everybody who experiences it, from resident to tourist or planner to politician.

Therefore it is relevant to begin this paper with a discussion of enquiry, rather than a seeking or needing to outline a definition for the issue. Bernard

Tschumi’s ‘questions of space’ in Architecture And Disjuncture proposes that space is something of an ‘open platform’, a discussion, as opposed to a statement of intent

“2.1 If perceptions differ, do they constitute different worlds that are the products of one’s past experience?”

2.2 If space consciousness is based on one’s respective experience, then does the perception of space involve a gradual construction rather than a ready-made schema?

2.21 Does this gradual construction contain elements that have a degree of invariance, such as archetypes?

2.3 Are spatial archetypes inevitably of a universal elementary nature, or can they include personal idiosyncrasies?

2.4” If space is a basic priori category of consciousness, independent of matter, is it an instrument of knowledge?

2.5 Is an instrument of knowledge the medium of experience?”¹

Across a series of 65 questions Tschumi advocates that the understanding of space, in the urban environment, is elusive, and, paradoxically, though it can satisfy any number of enquiries it persists in being indefinable.

It’s this ambiguity that makes the physical and perceptual space in cities so important, and so necessary that it demands that designers address these issues in a radically different manner than the current paradigm. It’s one of the concerns common to all post-industrial cities during the last 40 years; the attempts to define the renewal of the urban environment is an ongoing discussion in architectural, urban planning and public realm design offices. But are they simply striving to find answers to the problem, as opposed to redefining the questions it poses?

1.1 GLASGOW’S APPROACH TO SPACE

Since the 1990’s the City of Glasgow, in Scotland, has gained a reputation for innovative and successful urban regeneration through public realm projects.

¹ Tschumi, Bernard. Architecture and Disjunction. MIT Press 1998

Working in combination with key stakeholders and partners, the council have been the driving force behind this redevelopment - they are currently investigating new approaches, focusing on highly visual, engaging regeneration in the lead-up to the Commonwealth Games in 2012.

The key issue that will be addressed in an invigorated strategy is that of vacant and derelict land. According to the latest Urban Regeneration plan for the city, there is over 1325.76 ha (920 sites) of vacant and derelict land in Glasgow (7.52 % of the City). These holes in the fabric of the City have been accelerated by the recent global economic downturn and the rationalisation of public buildings such as schools.²

With the Glasgow Metropolitan region having 4566 hectares of derelict and vacant land³ in total, the real scale of the obstacle is established.

Those sites are frequently in residential neighbourhoods, often in the most deprived areas.⁴ And whilst these could, and arguably should, be designated temporarily⁵ for food growing, play areas, parks or any number of other uses, they are not. Perhaps because the public have differing needs. Perhaps because that need is the product of individual perception, based on individual experience. Perhaps this is why there's a great lack of action, in regard to derelict space.

Whatever the reason, the question of space, in regard to city centres, is not simple.

1.2 GLASGOW - DEAR GREEN PLACE

City dwellers and users have a multitude of needs from city spaces, so too do the local businesses and the council; but those uses aren't being assessed or advanced effectively.⁶ With a pressing concern about

²<http://www.glasgow.gov.uk/en/AboutGlasgow/Factsheets/Glasgow/Urban+Regeneration.htm>

³ Scottish Derelict and Vacant Land Survey 2007, published January 2008, The Scottish Government

⁴ 59.1% of Glasgow City's population lives within 500m of a derelict site, and 46% of all derelict and urban vacant land is within 15% of the most deprived areas, Derelict and Vacant Land Survey 2007 (as above)

⁵ In Glasgow vacant urban land can take between 1 and 10 years to transition from a neglected site to a building site. The term 'temporary' implies a state that has a limit, an end-point. But in the city centre there often isn't a fixed time-frame.

⁶ As part of their baseline study with the Merchant City Initiative, Graven Images have run a series of workshops with local residents and businesses to establish potential directions for open spaces in that specific area. From this, it's noted that there is broad commonality from the needs expressed. Most have a desire for 'guerilla greening' to happen in local spaces, for there to be temporary interventions even for a day or two, on streets, shopfronts, public space. They don't

environmental & urban conservation - over food sustainability in particular - for a rising metropolitan population, access to space is prominent in social consciousness, even Glasgow's. Its precedence ought to create more progress, faster, in the future, when the subject of city space comes up. Indeed, Glasgow City Council⁷ has implemented a series of successful 'greening' projects carried out under the Stalled Spaces programme - over the past 3 years, Glasgow's Development and Regeneration Service in partnership with other agencies, have worked with housing associations, groups and architects/developers to activate empty land near, or attached to, residential developments.

The Stalled Spaces report notes that there is an increase in landowners 'banking' space because of the current economic recession and decreased demand - they are retaining the sites or clearing them but not developing or regenerating them until there's a stronger financial climate.⁸

One key example of how this council initiative capitalises on that delay is The Botany project in Maryhill, Glasgow. Instigated by the Glasgow City Council Development and Regeneration Services (GCC:DRS) team in collaboration with British Waterways and ISIS Waterside Regeneration (GCC) the scheme addressed multiple sites within one neighbourhood. The landscaping approach included areas for growing, with wild-flower meadows and an orchard next to the new housing development - all easily adaptable to different uses and development. On completion, they were handed over to local community groups - supported by local organisations to run. Which creates a positive project model for real bottom-up growth.⁹

The Stalled Spaces scheme is a prime example of being able to address neglected space for the benefit of a local community, but it depends largely on local council, government and public sector input to instigate that change of use. All the Stalled Spaces projects involve a core group from various departments or associate agencies of the council.

Despite the undisputed success of the programme, DRS have yet to use it to confront any city centre spaces. Why is this?

actually want permanent solutions and grand masterplans, they want small spontaneous 'happenings' which would add spark to the neighborhood.

⁷ The Department of Regeneration Services is a division of the Glasgow City Council, whose focus is on fostering developments within the urban area which benefit communities, health, land value, civic growth fundamentally through public realm approaches.

⁸ Stalled Spaces - Temporary Landscapes, report, Glasgow City Council, 2011

⁹http://www.glasgow.gov.uk/en/Business/Environment/Clyde_KelvinGreenspace/Inspiring+Examples+The+Botany.htm

Within the scope of the 'Sow and Grow Everywhere' (SAGE) report¹⁰ ERZ, a leading Scottish landscape architecture practice, acknowledges that while they have progressed 3 strands of development addressing derelict land - via case study sites - the one strand concerned with a city centre area hasn't gained any momentum, community support, land owner or council input.¹¹ In discussing that particular site, the statement 'from visual inspection it offers a fairly level cleared site with no immediate evidence of a development intention'¹² not only supports Tschumi's notion that perception of space is based on individual experience, but it confirms that city centre space is largely unquantifiable. As evidenced by ERZ in that study, restrictions and access issues mean that urban space can't be accurately assessed, even at an initial research stage, let alone developed into active places.

If the site is privately owned, the logistics of allowing access to the land, the responsibilities and costs that come with that, are prohibitive - it costs less for the owner to keep it unused. Which may be the scenario indicated by the urban space discussed within the SAGE report.

1.3 GLASGOW - DEAR CONFLICTED PLACE

A notable example of disputed and unresolved space in Glasgow's city centre is the 'Selfridges site' in the Merchant City, the heart of Glasgow city centre - a combination of open space and unoccupied buildings spanning an entire city block, as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Top left, view of the Selfridges site taken from Argyle Street & Candleriggs. top right, Candleriggs looking toward the Argyle Street corner.

¹⁰ SAGE, 'Sow and Grow Everywhere', report by ERZ. Commissioned by Glasgow and Clyde Valley Green Network Partnership in February 2009 to create a strategic study focused on 'urban food growing' in the Glasgow Metropolitan region.

¹¹ To exemplify their range of project types, ERZ investigated 3 sites and developed proposals. Site 1. 'generic' urban derelict/vacant site: growing as an interim land use on derelict/vacant land in core urban areas. It's based on a site on Victoria Road in Govanhill in Glasgow. Extract from SAGE Report, 2007, p.62

¹² As above

Purchased by the retailer in 2002 to become a 200,000ft iconic Scottish flagship store designed by Japanese architect Toyo Ito, 9 years later it is still lying vacant. The negative, long-term impact of this site having remained derelict for almost 10 years is immense. The immediate area has seen a decline in business and footfall, decreasing land values and income due - in large part - to the appearance of this space

*"A high failure rate is common for new enterprises and the area is particularly vulnerable to the threats posed by a low pedestrian footfall away from the honey-pot' of Buchanan Street (Glasgow's prime retail street), relatively high city centre rates bills and the Selfridges factor' - the continuing depressive effect of two entire city centre blocks lying vacant at the heart of the area."*¹³

In an attempt to avoid the replication of this long-term, non-active space having such a negative impact on the city, the city council approved a motion - by Bailie Dr Nina Baker, supported by Councillor Philip Braat - to provide short-term public green space on vacant development sites in Glasgow¹⁴

*"The Council's City Plan 2 encourages the use of vacant and derelict land as temporary greenspace. I am delighted that the Council has resolved to work with site and property owners to temporarily landscape vacant sites to create simple and well-maintained grassed areas that will be open to the public..."*¹⁵

Despite Dr Baker's progress with the motion 2 years ago, in April 2011 temporarily greened spaces have yet to appear in the city centre. This indicates that even with positive energy, and council endorsement, Glaswegian city centre space remains unexploited, unquestioned, in the short to medium term.

In considering both the council's agreement to, and lack of progress with, temporary greening in the centre, it's apparent that the approach taken on The Botany site is something that doesn't work in the city. With the 'Selfridges' site, one can see that inaction creates a negative expanse much greater than the site itself. In the conversation surrounding the Merchant City environment, silence has arguably been far more detrimental than responding with the wrong answer.

¹³ extract from a Glasgow City Council report, cited in 'Selfridges under fire in regeneration plan', by Chris Musson, 12th June 2007, <http://www.eveningtimes.co.uk>

¹⁴ motion raised at Glasgow City Council meeting, 30th October 2008

¹⁵ Bailie Dr Baker, http://news.bbc.co.uk/1/hi/scotland/glasgow_and_west/7700418.stm

2. RE-ENGAGING SPACES IN A CITY

The SAGE report looked at 3 exemplar projects that reflected its “4 strands of activity”,¹⁶ what if - in regard to city centre vacant land issues - the key focus wasn't on the activity, was not on filling the space with something, but is instead on exploring understanding and the temporary interpretations of space through that activity?

The lack of action in regard to city centre spaces enhances a lack of definition, which in turn determines new use: attracting people who see the neglected site as a destination primarily because it is an undervalued and forgotten place. This activity isn't regarded in a general discussion about regenerating neglected sites and stalled spaces, because it is seen to be symptomatic of neglect: action to be discouraged. However, their actions do turn a space, into a real place, and are therefore relevant when considering informal, unconscious descriptions of the urban landscape.

With a construction industry in decline, and new building projects put on hold due to the economy, gap sites and empty spaces in the city centre will become something of a permanent temporary feature. In this context it is vital that in a discussion of space, new ways to understand the problem are at the top of the agenda. To create a new approach to urban design, to create a new type of city, the focus will not be on definition, but one centred on building *methods* for questioning those spaces.

2.1 GLASGOW - A CASE STUDY SITE FOR A NEW LINE OF QUESTIONING

¹⁶ The overall strategy has 4 parallel strands of activity, as follows: strategy strand 1: bring vacant & derelict land in densely populated urban areas into use for growing as an interim land use. Strategy strand 2: bring underused land (amenity space) in peripheral estates & social housing areas into use at scales up to market garden growing. Strategy strand 3: bring underused private garden space in suburban or outlying areas into use for growing. Strategy strand 4: bring underused public land into active use for growing (focused on schools throughout the area)

Figure 2 Taken from a rooftop terrace, this photograph shows the case study area which lies in the northern part of the Merchant City, Glasgow.

As a barometer for this spatial analysis and questioning, a case study site - 2 enclosed, secured areas containing low-level vegetation and trees, between College Street, Albion Street & George Street - which has been empty since 2004, was selected for visual analysis. Figure 2, above.

The area is 3 large sections of land, divided by pedestrian routes and low-volume roads, creating an expansive barrier between Strathclyde University and the cultural hub of the Merchant City. It's an anonymous zone, which has become as much of a feature in the area as an iconic building. It's used as a 'marker' when describing routes or this part of the city. And due to low footfall, it's synonymous with illegal activity despite being in a very central location. Over the years it's been the subject of many uses: a rugby playing field, goals for football, a place for friends to meet to smoke together, a drinking place, somewhere to hold protest rallies ... For one man, the central section has become his personal running track; almost every weekday evening for 3 years, he has run around and around that space.

From a nearby observation point (the roof of a building) the case study area appears as a stage for all this activity; with each new person taking on a new role in the 'play of space'.

By investigating examples of usage, this particular case study examining abandoned space may be interpreted (though not necessarily activated or repurposed) into the development of a new approach to the urban conversation.

The users of this case study site respond to both its, and their, perception of space; supporting the line of questioning that alludes to space being intuitive, that experience of the space, not the space itself, forms a definition.¹⁷

In summary, four general types of use or activity take place on and around this site: migration, imagination, appropriation, and leisure.

2.2 PERFORMANCE OF, AND IN, A SPACE

If the built environment has a dialogue, then the users of this area are characters cut & pasted into the script during the dress rehearsal. They're temporal - they come into the space to do something specific, and then disappear back into

¹⁷ Tschumi, Bernard. *Architecture and Disjunction*. MIT Press 1998

the city pattern. They migrate in and out of the case study site creating a play on it's stage for an evening, weeks, or sometimes sporadically over months & years.

With this, theatre of space, notion, it's relevant to consider another post-industrial city. Glasgow in 2011 echoes the regeneration, socio-economic decline and urban 'sustainability' focus of New York during the 70's.

In response to that environment Vito Acconci (1940 -) created 'found poetry' in the late 60's by dislocating word's from their original context and putting them together a-new on the page; abstracted from an original text and inserted into another, those words carried and created layers of new meaning. The actions of four different user types - as above- take place within the structure of the one urban space, similar to the white page Acconci worked with. The actions - if treated as adjectives in a sentence - overlay, creating a narrative that reads as a more complete description of space.

"As Acconci cut, spliced, moved and displaced words, he performed many of the principle actions of the new sculpture. These actions became increasingly performative, as Acconci asked himself; "if I'm so interested in this question of space and movement over a page, why am I confining this movement to an 8 x 11 inch piece of paper?" From here, he began to operate in a variety of media, exploring the real space of human interactions, and creating some of the foundational works of performance art."¹⁸

To fully explore movement and space he worked from the page, then to the place and performance. In the case of the contemporary city centre, that course of action has been tried and tested. If this process is reversed - allowing space, performance and action to dictate the language and conversation about urban space - could it script a more accurate line of design questioning in the city? Could it encourage users to ask the questions?

In the case of James, who lived on the site in a homemade, corrugated metal shelter, what are the semiotics of his occupation of the site? What words does he lend to the space?

He and his friends had all used the site at some point over the years as a place to sleep at night. Perhaps because of that, they said that they'd happily help the local authorities to clean it up, they'd like the opportunity to do something good for the area. A contradiction of the common opinion that homeless people and 'mis-use' of empty city spaces is clearly detrimental to communities. "Quiet. Still. An oasis. Escape". Soft words would be his contribution to the dialogue. As he told the author the day they went into the site, this bit of derelict land was his

"...own private park, nobody comes in here, nobody knows I'm here, it's the best place I've ever lived, and I'm 43 and I've lived all over the place!"¹⁹

For James, this space was peaceful, secret and safe, despite it being such an open and public area. He settled down to live there, albeit temporarily.

Figure 3 A group of teenagers under the trees and in the open, drinking

Figure 4 The contrast between public & private, open & closed, interior & exterior is blurred by this particular couple have sex in the space.

While James was living there, teenagers would come in to drink in the wooded part of the site, near his shelter. They were more wary of being in the site, of being caught, and their movements less linear and more 'jagged'. The space became a platform for socialising and networking within their group. For these users, the space takes on different adjectives, and different symbolic movements. Darting. Jagged.

¹⁹ Extract from an informal interview conducted whilst photographing the largest part of the case study site between Albion Street, George Street space - James and two friends from a nearby hostel were drinking in the wooded area. All of them had used the site at some point over the years as a place to sleep at night because they knew the police didn't go in there to look for people. Interestingly, they said that they'd happily help the local authorities to clean it up, they'd like the opportunity to do something good. Which contradicts the common opinion that homeless people and 'mis-use' of empty city spaces is detrimental to communities.

¹⁸ Acconci, Vito. Extract from artist biography, Institute of Contemporary Arts. <http://www.ica.org.uk>

Furtive. Starts small & contained, but gets bigger, bolder and less restrained, figures 3 & 4, below.

2.3 SYMBOLISM OF PATTERNS IN SPACE

In addition to the illicit occupiers of the site, there are the stakeholders who put up advertising and event posters around the site. Although they don't access the internal space, and their activity - in contrast to the others - is legal, it does prompt movement that defines the area; people slow down, or stop at unusual, unplanned intervals around the site to read posters. Some, whilst reading, make a call or light a cigarette, which encourages them to slowly pace back & forth along small sections of the boundary. Methodical. Restrained. Repetition. Stop & start. Smooth linear movement along the perimeter line, interrupted by stopping and starting then returning to a regular pace.

These temporal occupations of space - combined with the appropriation of the perimeters for meeting, dwelling or recreation (figure 5) - build up a story, a series of signs, which read as a pattern distinct to urban gapsites. The jagged, frenetic shapes combined with the static flat and tall lines of other movements to create something quite intricate: decorative instructions allowing us to understand the form. Now the beginnings of a methodology are apparent; questioning empty urban spaces through movement, not necessarily through specifying an activity that happens in, on, or around it.

Figure 5 The perimeter of these sites, in the case study area, are used for a multitude of different activities that take place simultaneously. This shot shows BMX riders jumping off the steps and using the open space for practicing tricks, alongside people sitting down to have a cigarette and make phone calls. The activities overlap without any conflict, and often at the same time as others are using the interior of the central site.

2.4 PATTERNS OF MOVEMENT

By looking at the combined emotive and intuitive

responses of people who use spaces in the city centre, we can follow their steps to realise the Site's full potential through design.

The start-point in any design process is observation (figure 5) then usually there's a period of intuitive and informed sketching & designing. Figures 6 & 7 (right) show a selection of drawings created by the author whilst observing activity in the site. The spontaneous and quick drawn sketches capture the essence of the activities, their shapes and forms. Whilst an analytical series of drawings may be more appropriate to a research discussion, these intuitive responses echo the notion that space is best described as a collection of personal reactions. These drawings are the beginning of a design response to the case study space.

Figure 6 First impressions of how some of the people - as discussed - use the space, translated as a series of overlaid, triangular forms

Figure 7 Quickly drawing the specific routes/activity around the site led to a triangular 'pattern'. These lines could potentially inform how design might translate movement into an approach to space.

In reducing the movements of the users, without conscious reasoning, to lines & shapes, their actions become the subject of space. They become the abstract depiction of what space could be.

2.5 MOVEMENT CREATES PATTERNS IN SPACE

Within her earlier work in the 70's, New York artist and performer Trisha Brown used the urban environment of Soho as the subject matter and stage for performance. In collaboration with artist Donald Judd 'Newark (Niweorce)', 1987, explored both their interests in defining and controlling space, to it's fullest. The performance used seriality and repetition to reduce elements and movements down to their purest, simplest forms. Movement was limited, and to simulate the control of space and time, the stage depth - subsequently too the dancers performance space - was gradually shortened with moving panels of saturated colour. The background environment moves, so the dancers move in response to those shifts. Which, from observing the empty sites between Albion Street, George Street and College Street in Glasgow, is what the public were unconsciously doing with the empty space in their city environment.

As part of MoMA's 'On Line: Drawing Through the Twentieth Century' exhibition in 2011, the Trisha Brown Dance Company performed several pieces that explored those themes of space, control, and repetition further. With specific reference to one piece, Scallops, the dancers pivoted around the perimeter of a square in a sequence of movements that demonstrated an orderly yet unpredictable pattern; following the line but through their own interpretation.

Commenting on the inclusion of dance in a drawing exhibition, curators Connie Butler and Catherine de Zegher noted that

*"It's essence is the line - 'the trace of a point in motion' - which can be drawn not just on the page, but in space and time. It's a definition that accommodates a variety of expressive media, including the human body in deliberate motion. All four of the works Brown has chosen to present explore the expressive potential inherent in the interplay of line, pattern, and movement stripped of extraneous gesture and overt virtuosity."*²⁰

Both Vito Acconci and Brown are a product of the 70's New York arts scene, and both disseminate the landscape, lines, words, and descriptions to pure movement in space. The parallel between this, and the members of the public in Glasgow is easy to see - exemplified by the drawings - so too is the broader discussion concerning the influence of the

urban environment in relation to styles of movement/action.

Dance - and music - 'scenes' such as, breaking, raving, voguing, krumping, tecktonic & brukup (to name a few of the more recognized genres) have grown as a direct response to the social experience of an urban environment.

Around the time that Trisha Brown was defying the rules of art & performance with 'roof piece' (1971) - a reaction to the social and political environment in New York City - uptown, in Harlem & the Bronx, teenagers were breakdancing on the streets. Both activities use the city as a stage. Both use movement to communicate emotional, social and spatial disenfranchisement to their audience. Both illustrate their lives in the city through the style of physical movements. And most significantly, both perform a description of the space that they occupy in an urban and social framework.

Looking at the movements, it could be said that the positions and shapes of breakdance physically address city conditions. The 1983 film 'Wild Style' by Charlie Ahearn documented this scene and in many ways, it exemplified the notion of performance creating personal perimeters & spaces within the city.

The angles of the body, the contorted shapes and sharp poses of visually described life in 70's Harlem (figure 8). The physicality of the city is evident in his pose. Even in contemporary hiphop culture in the UK, the same parallels between environment and movement can be seen, see figures 9. Urban space can be demonstrated through dance.

Figure 8 The breakdance pose echoes the street-view - 1970's Harlem

²⁰ O'Connell, Kathleen. Pattern Recognition. Danceviewtimes, January 12th 2011

Figure 9 Trellick House, London. The spaces and tension of the limbs as well as the overall composition of the body reflect the inner-city tower.

In 2011 'brukup' captures the pulse of New York city again, flourishing in the space-deprived housing projects in Brooklyn. In the case of brukup it's not so much about using dance to create a space and show skills, but rather about building communities and using dance as a way to escape to a 'different space'. In a New York Times article, one dancer on the brukup scene, Mr Theague stated that

*"Dancing saved my life plenty of times. I had friends who were shot dead hanging out on the corner. I would have been there, too, if I wasn't out dancing somewhere."*²¹

The brukup groups use dance performances to draw a line between the real world and a fictitious second-life²², at times, as Mr Theague noted, it's actually between life and death in Bedford-Stuyvesant, Brooklyn.

Forty years prior, Trisha Brown's 'roof piece' (figure 9, below) depicted ephemeral semaphores sent across the rooftops of 10 blocks in downtown Manhattan - a performance projecting symbols into the skies above New York. Perhaps 'the city' has always been silently holding out for a [super] hero.

Figure 10 Trisha Brown's 'roof piece' with the symbolic hero of Gotham City and the Western World, Batman.

2.6 PATTERNS CREATE SPACE

By looking at these dances and performances it's notable that during the activity, space is divided and defined through the physical action. Taking this as a start-point, and breaking with conventional urban analysis,²³ could lead the public and professional stakeholders to initiate and undertake a more direct line of questioning spaces.

It could be said that a line is drawn between the character in the performance and their environment; sometimes connecting the two, at times encapsulating both, at others, that line allows the dancer autonomy and freedom. From this it can be argued that there is a boundary when space becomes a subject of activity, use & performance. And it's on this periphery that perceptions of that space and action are, ultimately, formed.

To develop a valid comprehension of space in the urban landscape, the design conversation needs to start with this idea of performance, and subsequent escapism, symbolism and movement, as the drawing. If action can define space, movement can draw the picture of it, and words can describe the feeling of space; surely this can be a relevant methodology for public realm design in our cities?

²¹ Che, Cathay. Brukup Follows an Afro-Caribbean Beat. The New York Times March 8th 2011

²² The dancers perform under pseudonyms adopting characteristics of kung fu masters, ninja warriors, circus ringmasters, old world heroes - aliases such as 'The Most Electrifying Man in Brooklyn', or 'Dominus The Conqueror' exemplify this escapism. This fantasy world created in the inner city housing estates of Brooklyn relates to the first of Tschumi's questions on the definition of space "2.1 If perceptions differ, do they constitute different worlds that are the products of one's past experience?"

²³ http://www.weburbandesign.com/pages/bluerings_s02.html

3. A NEW QUESTION FOR SPACE

Applying this to the Glasgow case study site, performance artist Kate E. Deeming was invited by the author to engage with the space.²⁴ Through an intuitive response to the physical environment and a discussion of the site observations during the previous month, the artist produced a series of controlled interpretations in the space. Within this performance Deeming began to define parameters of the site through sequential movements, building on actions of former users, initiating patterns and pathways shaped by form.

Dressed as an office worker - who was observed using the surrounding area during her lunch breaks - Deeming explored the fenced perimeter as that fictitious character. The real office worker had been seen sitting on a concrete bench eating a sandwich before strolling around the site, slowly, chatting on the phone, before returning in the direction of the city centre.

When this activity was re-imagined as a performance, the dancer paced the interior perimeter of the site trying to break free - reaching up to the sky, crouching down low behind the vegetation, pressing against the fence boards, climbing up, falling down. The peaks and troughs of the movement, juxtaposing the monotony of vertical fence-boards, creating a sense of muffled urgency, a quiet attempt to escape (figure 11). Perhaps an apt description of how an office worker might feel during their lunch-break.

Viewed as a sequence of movements along the fence, a pattern emerged. Her arbitrary action sat against the repetitive, staccato voice of the boundary-treatment; the ornament of pattern interrupts the narrative of the line. Through her movement, the dancer broke the perceived perimeter of the site - questioning the permanence and authority of the line. In doing so, she delineated space.

As shown in figure 12, if this performance were translated as a quick drawing, the shapes that Deeming made could be translated into a pattern that cuts through the line of the perimeter. It created a new line [of perception] that is engaged with both the exterior and interior of the divided space. In her performance she bridged the boundary

between the private interior and public exterior of the case study site. The performance created a pattern that captured multiple views and perceptions of a space, at once.

Figure 11 A couple of scenes from the performance by Kate E. Deeming

Figure 12 Annotation of the way the line is broken through movement, similar to how perception is altered through performance

²⁴ Kate E. Deeming, a New York native, has been dancing in Glasgow urban spaces for the past year. In various projects she has activated forgotten or undefined spaces in the city through dance. One particular exercise took place in the same space, everyday, for 2 months. Kate danced in the same spot on the riverfront, at 10am every morning. That un-programmed piece of the cityscape became a focal point. It captured both a regular and transient audience. It gained a definition, and this stimulated movement within the greater context of the city - people changed their routes, schedules and use of the city because of this happening. <http://www.deeming.org/>

3.1 INTERPRETING THE LINE

During a dance-architecture workshop, Carol Brown noted that Dance and Architecture have much in common. Both are concerned with practices of space. For a dancer the act of choreography as a writing of place occurs through the unfolding of spatial dimensions through gesture and embodied

movement. For the architect, space is the medium through which form emerges and habitation is constructed. For both, the first space we experience is the space of the body.²⁵

Collating multiple actions, gestures and descriptions to breakdown the image of a space, is not a new approach; it is applicable to re-consider its history in the context of this discussion of the city landscape. At the turn of the 19th century Paul Cezanne captured the same sense of layered perception as Deeming's fence-line performance, and Trisha Browns patterns of movement in 'roof piece'. The concept of overlaying multiple views of a scene in the one canvas, creating a multi-faceted, fractured image, forms the basis of the Cubist movement.²⁶

In analysing patterns of action in and around the case study site in Glasgow, there is a parallel with Cezanne's drive to capture a new sense of space: his intention was to show that it was not an empty domain in which object and planes are separated or exist in a relative sense, but that his space was full of essence.²⁷ His paintings discuss space in terms of four dimensions - the fourth being that of experience - what he described as 'essence'. This was captured through a technique of over-painting the scene from different perspectives, adding more texture and depth as those views multiplied, until the scene became an abstract compound of shapes and form creating their own landscape. His painting 'Lac d'Annecy' exemplifies this idea of sensation, essence, and creative impression of a space.

3.2 RE-BUILDING A SPACE

Through discussion of performance, description, shape, and, of momentary gestures, the case study site in Glasgow builds its own catalogue of spatial impressions. It creates a tangible, multi-faceted image of space without having to answer one specific question or designate one specific activity for the site.

With this, it can be concluded that space is best understood as layered fragments of stories, voices and movements. In regard to the issue of space in

cities then, the purpose of a design approach needs to be centred on capturing this layering; finding a way of conveying those fragments with enough capacity for them to be used by others to describe their own space.

At its core, an innovative framework for defining space will be focused on this new understanding, and on opening up that space by breaking down perception.

Agreeing that a layered methodology is the necessary approach to space is the first part of the long overdue conversation between city, user and space. These empty sites now require an applied practice for breaking down the peripheral, the edge; the boundaries of perception.

During her performance in the Glasgow site, Kate E. Deeming used repetitive movements that visually punch through the line of the perimeter - the shapes of those actions creating a jagged profile similar to the undergrowth, epitomising the combined emotional response of the site and the office worker.²⁸ Sigmund Freud compared the workings of the city to that of the mind in 'Civilisation and Its Discontents' - if space conveys feelings or responses through the actions, shapes and descriptions of its users, it is reasonable to say that space has emotive value.

Gordon Matta-Clark²⁹ was heavily influenced by Freud's concept, particularly that aspect concerning the underground regions, of a hidden city that could spill out into the controlled urban landscape, like repressed memories or unlawful impulses. His discourse with architecture builds in the lead-up to the Anarchitecture group exhibition (1974, Soho, New York City). He wrote intently on the subject of words, meanings and the role of text in constructing a relevant understanding of a city. In one letter he turns Louis Sullivan's dictum 'form follows function' to 'form follows function', as James Attlee notes

"If this wordplay means anything it implies that a rigid adherence to certain ideas of form will restrict an object or a building's usefulness. An opposite approach might be to allow an object's appearance to suggest spontaneous new uses..."³⁰

His project in New Jersey in 1974, 'Splitting', exemplifies this ideology of dissecting buildings, of cutting into, opening up and exposing interior as exterior space. In this piece, he cut a slice through the centre of a two-storey suburban house. Creating a disorientating inside-outside architectural vision

²⁸ Though a piece of derelict land is inanimate, devoid of human emotion, the essence, the impression of the space - as Cezanne asserts a landscape capable - is one of neglect and intermittent trauma.

²⁹ Gordon Matta-Clark (1943 - 1978)

³⁰ Attlee, James, Towards Anarchitecture: Gordon Matta-Clark And Le Corbusier. Tate Papers, Spring 2007

²⁵ Carol Brown, dance-architecture workshop, Isadora and Raymond Duncan Centre for Dance, 29 September - 5 October 2003

²⁶ Inaugurated by Georges Braque and Pablo Picasso between 1907 and 1914, Cubism emphasized the flat, two-dimensional surface of the picture plane. Adopting an approach of spatial deconstruction, these painters rejected the traditional techniques. In a general sense it could be said that Cubism is trying to show all sides of the depicted objects simultaneously. That it violates the unified space of simple perspective to show each object from its canonical viewpoint, regardless of the relation of the other objects.

²⁷ Tyler, Christopher W. Ione, Amy. The Concept of Space in Twentieth Century Art

that not only engaged the visitor in dividing the space, but the elements and weather too. Exploring Cezanne's 'impression of space' in the fullest sense.

Matta-Clark allowed boundaries to shift and new permutations of space to dictate shape. He replaced architecture with space of collapse and removal. He questioned architecture through symbolic and aesthetic interventions in structural space. Matta-Clark played on the limit of architecture.

Attlee quotes the transcript from 'The Anarchitect'³¹ as saying that Matta-Clark was '...really very much interested in this idea that the city had a life which was in the air, it had a life which is on the ground and it had a life below the ground...' This is exactly what Cezanne was capturing with his multi-faceted impression of space on the canvas. It's what Acconci was achieving by dislocating words and performing them on the cityscape. It's what Brown symbolised on the rooftops of New York. It's why teenagers are dressing as clowns and krumping in LA.

What unites all the artists, performers, and users that have been discussed within this paper is that they were trying to create or symbolise space through their actions. What cities currently have is space, what it doesn't have is the methodology to frame it so that space can be understood, and performed on to a greater extent in the future. Following Matta-Clark's order - opening up the architecture [of space] with cutting, splitting, extracting and activity - to convey the layers that the users of the Glasgow site created, could give the patterns, symbols and words an activity inside the design process. What is the actual space was left as the question, but the design action was applied to the line in-between space and the city?

In the way that Matta-Clark cut through his buildings, the perimeter of sites could be used as the translator for the performance of space. In the way that Trisha Brown choreographed dance on rooftops, down the side of buildings, on interior walls and in shapes. In the mode of Acconci cutting out words, realigning them on a new piece of paper. Following the style of teenagers dressing as fictitious characters from a long-lost empire to do brukup in Bed-Stuy.

The perimeter line could metaphorically thin-slice the space, encouraging it to become accessible to everybody, letting its facets activate the urban landscape.

3.3 IN-BETWEEN A SPACE

Taking this toward a design proposal - based around the case area analysis - draws an interesting parallel

between what was witnessed, and a personal 'performance' of that same site. It questions what has been concluded about space, and also what's most relevant about this design process; it continues to ask questions. It draws into focus the very nature of the perception that was analysed.

A 3rd floor apartment offered an ideal vantage point to observe the case study area. From that perspective, the derelict land looked like lush oasis in the city. It was an idyllic vision of the space. Altering routes through the city to walk past the case study area on a regular basis, it became apparent that although there was greenery from the window, on the street the only experience is fence boards. Thousands of tall, bland, repetitive fence boards. The more journeys taken around the space, the more oppressive the perimeter became. Knowing that something so picturesque and engaging was on the other side of that tall fence made the boundary of the space even more of a negative experience.

When Kate E. Deeming explored the space with dance, her behaviour and reaction to the exterior reflects the dichotomy of that 'line' in the understanding of this particular space.

Figure 13 Deeming 'falling off the line' of perception

The contrast between this reaction in figure 13, outside the space and that of figure 14 (below), inside the space, shows how relevant Matta-Clark's 'Splitting' piece is in the discussion of attainable space.

³¹ The Anarchitect, film by Jane Crawford, Gordon Matta-Clark archive at the Canadian Centre for Architecture

Figure 14 Deeming 'inside' one of the case study sites

Sitting in the open plaza area felt exposed. Applying the same method of observation as practised with other users, the experience can be summarised as: vulnerable, isolated, small, and self-conscious. Sitting on the bench - where the office worker character had her lunch - there is nothing to look at. The only thing to do is make calls & send emails on a phone, just like those who'd been observed from the 3rd floor viewpoint.

The undeniable conclusion of this experience is an assemblage of the 3rd floor halcyon view; the oppressive street experience, layered with a broad subconscious knowledge of patterns.

4. DESIGNING FOR A SPACE

Focusing on the contrast between the interior and exterior of this space, the design process undertaken by the author looked at how the perimeter might become a tool for combining two sides of the story. Like every other user, this design approach brought personal history and understanding to the space; the initial design developments incorporate descriptions & images of users movements, references to archive lace, but primarily, they drew on the shapes of the plant-life pushing through the gaps in the fence-boards.

Figure 15 Fencing around the central section of the case study area

The underlying design concept for the Trellis

proposal was to create a perimeter treatment that encourages views into the space, and encourages that site to spill out. With those simple actions, the merged contexts can engage public perception. Instead of being a wall of bland fence-boards, this 'splitting' of the boundary, encourages greenery and colour to open up the street. It becomes a platform which can change with every step and movement, and on each different site, the 'splitting' being designed to directly reflect the specific setting.

Through the shattering of the boundary-line, a new healthier more engaging environment could be created; one, which doesn't require large areas of land to communicate its message.

The proposal was that a boundary area of 1m was taken around the interior perimeter line, and planted to enhance the existing vegetation, creating an urban hedgerow seen through the 'broken' fence line. With the incorporation of a structural support system, saplings as well as plants could be grown - increasing the amount of trees in pedestrian areas without encroaching on public walkways. In turn, this hedgerow provides a habitat for insects, bees & butterflies and has an impact on water run-off in the city centre (an expensive and increasingly major issue for Glasgow City Council).

Figure 16 adjustable systems of cables run from a series of vertical wrought iron ballustrade pieces to create a trellis for growing inside the site. Extract from Trellis proposal document

The real innovation comes from an approach that reflects the temporal nature of the site activity. All the movements and uses of the case study site were fleeting. The artists discussed, performed actions and interpretations of their space for a fixed period of time. The problem of empty city centre space is it's indefinite existence, its lack of fixed time and lack of interim relevance - something identified in leading Scottish Design Consultancy, Graven Images, Baseline Study for the Merchant City Initiative (see reference 6).

What if space had an identity for the period when it was in-between use, and what if that identity was a medium for interpretation? Space would become a more tangible experience.

The Trellis design proposal addresses this by creating

a flexible system that utilises existing perimeter materials and structural elements but cuts into them to create surface, a collage of dissected elements around the perimeter (see figure 16). This approach doesn't need to be permanently built into the space; it can be inserted, used as a tool for engaging with the space then moved on to another. By using what is already there, the proposal eliminates the substantial up-front costs, security fears regarding perimeter strength and it repurposes existing knowledge/skills. In a similar way to Trisha Brown using the language of the skyline in 'Roof Piece', the temporary perimeter structures create a series of transient semaphores across an existing framework.

Currently in discussion with GCC:DRS for use on 2 city centre sites in Glasgow, the Trellis design proposal aims to apply the methodology of its research toward building a suite of flexible perimeter treatments for commercial use. Each site has a different language, a different set of performances, and so although the basic model would be standard, each design response to the space will develop intuitively.

Figure 17 Extract from Trellis design proposal document

5. A QUESTION OF SPACE - CONCLUSION

James, the homeless 'resident' of the case study site, saw the space as his escape, and the Trellis design proposal builds on this to create a place that needs to escape. The teenagers used the space as place to hide, to feel free; and the Trellis design proposal reflects a feeling of confinement.

These contradictory experiences have built a surprising continuity in the translation of space. A collage of the imagery produced in this paper - the line drawings charting users moving around the space, the words attached to the site throughout

the process, sequenced movements made by Kate E. Deeming, the images of the plants, and the initial design proposal - demonstrate a repetition of homologous shapes, the same formations and sensation.

This proves that despite the diversity of understanding, of perceptions derived from varied past experiences, it does appear that every user fashioned the same essential spatial archetype. When viewed together, each engagement with this space uses triangular shapes, repeating forms, with a shattered, fractured application to the structure of space - be it addressing liminal use or the site itself.

Which, to return to the last three of Tschumi's questions as quoted at the very beginning of this paper, indicates that space does have an elemental universality, it does include personal idiosyncrasies yet it is not defined by them - proven by multiple independent users from a broad spectrum of experience and society creating the same forms in response to one space.

"2.3 Are spatial archetypes inevitably of a universal elementary nature, or can they include personal idiosyncrasies?"

2.4 If space is a basic priori category of consciousness, independent of matter, is it an instrument of knowledge?"

2.5 Is an instrument of knowledge the medium of experience?"³²

Space is an impression - compounding the elusiveness first noted - which everybody is susceptible to. It is, as the last of Tschumi's questions implies, a temporary composition - an influence in the subconscious and experience, one stronger than individual perception. Space in the urban landscape is a mutable sensation activated by performance.

Einstein proposed a quantum interpretation of space that, instead of being a void, consisted of an evanescence of particle creations and annihilations. In his theory of general relativity, he stated that the ticking rate of a clock depends on the motion of the observer of that clock. And if gravity, as well as motion, can render intervals of time and of space indefinite in scientific theory, why seek certainty from space in the contemporary city?

With economic decline, falling standards of living and social disillusion, the city as it once was, is no more. The only way to create a city as it might be is to embrace uncertainty, to pose questions that will help build tools for the urban landscape. Within the scope of the Trellis project a new design

³² Architecture and Disjunction, Bernard Tschumi, published by MIT Press

methodology within public realm design is forming. It reads the contemporary city, across perception and performance, leaving space as a place open to definition.

"It is not necessary to create a world, but the possibility of a world", ³³

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³³ Jean Luc-Godard, 1985